

MULTI-STAGE OPTIMIZATION FLEXIBILITY ALGORITHM FOR DEMAND RESPONSE IN ANCILLARY SERVICES. AN INDUSTRIAL CASE STUDY

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Abstract

To ensure that future electrical distribution networks can effectively meet the dynamic demands of the evolving energy landscape due to the penetration of renewable energy sources, the energy-oriented industrial sector has the opportunity to enhance hosting grid capacity in response to short-term requests from system operators. This is achieved by increasing energy resources available to the grid through flexible capacity offers, aiming to prevent periods of system instability. This flexibility has traditionally been provided by large generators on the supply-side, but new opportunities for demand-side flexibility can be integrated into the industrial sector through incentive-based demand response programs. One option is to strategically allocate capacity for balancing service markets through load reduction curves. While large consumers may compete against generators in flexibility-markets, small and medium-sized industries remain largely unexplored. This paper builds on a flexible multi-single machine manufacturing problem and proposes a method for providing day-ahead demand-side flexibility offers combined with price-based real-time pricing demand response. The study is approached from the perspective of a non-intensive industry under an aggregator platform, enabling participation in balancing service auctions. The paper also examines the viability and applicability of flexibility offers within the constraints of low-capacity offers, to determine the optimal flexibility strategy.

1. Introduction

Demand response (DR) programs constitute a set of mechanisms aimed at improving grid flexibility, with the increase in variable renewable energy sources (RES) penetration in electric grids, as one of the main reasons. Supply-side flexibility alone cannot cover the flexibility requirements for integrating RES, emphasizing the need for new potential sources of flexibility. In this context demand-side flexibility has great potential [1]. The main classification of DR programs consists of price-based programs and incentive-based programs [2]. Price-based programs motivate consumers to improve load consumption patterns in response to changes in electricity prices by implementing electricity tariffs such as Time-of-Use (TOU) or Real-Time Pricing (RTP) [3], while incentive-based programs offer financial incentives to consumers to reduce their load consumption for a period of time during high wholesale market prices or when grid reliability is at risk. For an industrial consumer, both strategies can be combined from a demand-side management perspective. Incentive-based programs can be a way to provide demand-side flexibility from the industrial sector, through load reduction curve (LRC) offers for balancing service markets (BSMs).

Large-scale demand-side flexibility constitutes the most cost-effective demand-side flexibility [4] that can compete against generators and energy distributors in the BSMs. While large-scale industry consumers have been widely studied [5], there is a literature gap in unlocking such flexibility for small and medium-sized industries. However, small and medium-sized industries might face challenges in meeting the minimum capacity offer to enter the BSM auctions. Hence, this work is built upon the context of an aggregator, for the proposed LRC offers to reach the required minimum flexibility to allow the industry to compete in the BSMs.

On the electricity market front, European flexibility-markets identify conventional BSMs, including Frequency Containment Reserves (FCR), automatic and manual Frequency Restoration Reserves (aFRR and mFRR), and Replacement Reserves (RR) [6]. Participating in BSMs can increase revenue for industries by employing operational strategies, such as submitting flexibility offers in the day-ahead market. This involves solving scheduling problems and imposing constraints on energy consumption during specific time periods, while considering the market's payment for

capacity reservation [7]. These consumption reductions serve as energy reserves for the market, with companies aiming to strike an optimal balance between lowering production costs, including energy purchase costs, and maximizing energy reserve sales. In this paper, a medium-sized industry is used as a case study, based on Standard Profil Spain (SPS), a Spanish company focused only on sealing systems for the automobile market. The study aims to generate flexibility offers within an aggregator platform operating in the Spanish market, paving the way for future participation of small and medium-size industries in European BSMs.

2. Methodology

A multi-stage optimization constraint programming algorithm has been developed (Fig. 1) for submitting flexibility offers to an aggregator. The algorithm takes energy data, such as the hourly price of the spot-market electricity tariff and the consumption of the production process as input, as well as scheduling data from workers availability and shared resources, to optimize a scheduling plan, referred to as the baseline model. Then, several flexibility offers, through LRCs, are calculated based on the baseline load profile from the baseline solution and the ancillary service constraints. This is done in the flexibility model by optimizing the scheduling plan with the provided flexibility. Incorporating different ancillary service constraints into the flexibility model enables participation in various services within tertiary reserve markets, such as mFRR or RR. The flexibility model serves as the framework for adjusting the baseline model to accommodate the LRC.

Fig. 1 Multi-stage optimization scheme

2.1. Baseline model

The baseline production process of the case study comprises four continuous rubber extrusion lines, where each line produces different rubber profiles used in sealing systems. A line is modelled as a single machine with sequence-dependent set-ups. The aim of the production scheduling is to sequence consecutive jobs according to the lines' capacity to meet the desired production. Only one job can be processed by a machine at a time. Jobs can be interrupted to provide flexible

LRCs, but demand has to be recovered for the whole production horizon of 5 working days.

The energy vector is integrated into the baseline model scheduling plan, minimizing production costs. These costs consist of energy and material costs of the scheduling plan, taking into account electricity and gas consumption. The optimal scheduling considers constraints from the single-machine problem, shared resources, demand constraints, as well as worker availability for machine operation and shift-constrained operations.

2.2. Flexibility model

The objective function cost of the flexibility model is derived from the baseline model's objective function cost, which is represented by the summation term of equation (1). This cost is adjusted by subtracting a profit, denoted as the negative term in (1). The profit is calculated as the product of the constant power capacity offered to the grid in kW multiplied by the flexibility period (FP) the service is active, with an upper bound of the bid (M) in €/kWh. A constant load offer makes the offered energy block indivisible and increases the likelihood of acceptance by the BSMs [8]. The negative sign in (1) serves to maximize the profit term inside the minimization function. Flexibility offers are created by maximizing the energy capacity offered to the day-ahead market through different FPs while minimizing production costs.

$$(1) \quad [Min] \sum_{(i,j) \in J} \left(E(batch_{i,j}) + \gamma_{i,j} \times \text{precenceOf}(batch_{i,j}) \right) - Capacity \times FP \times M$$

$batch_{i,j}$: Optional interval variable indicating operation from consecutive job pairs $(i, j) \in J$, from the set of jobs J .

$\text{precenceOf}(a)$: If optional interval a is present, it returns 1; 0 otherwise.

$E(a)$: Energy cost variable of an optional batch interval a in €.

$\gamma_{i,j}$: material loss cost parameter in €, of consecutive job pair $(i, j) \in J$, from the set of jobs J .

Offering the maximum available capacity for the day-ahead market helps create an aggregated offer that can compete in the BSMs. This is achieved by assigning the bound M to the bid of the offered capacity during the FP . Once the solution is obtained, the minimum bid (2) required to compensate for the activation cost of the flexibility is calculated. It takes into account the cost increase with the rescheduling in € of the flexibility model cost solution ($FlexibilityCost$), with respect to the baseline model cost solution ($BaselineCost$) and added management cost (MC) if the total production from the day-ahead is altered, divided by the total energy in MWh provided to the grid, plus a contribution margin.

$$(2) \quad Bid = \frac{FlexibilityCost - BaselineCost + MC}{Capacity \times FP}$$

Previous to the day-ahead, the industry determines its potential for LRCs compared to the available baseline load for different

upcoming *FPs*, after a potential start for the LRC at the activation time (T_A). The flexibility offers imply shifting or curtailing loads in the most cost-effective way. The industry sends as many flexibility offers as possible to the aggregator once a day, within the scheduling constraints, featuring various T_A and capacities. Only one offer will be executed for the day-ahead to avoid time-dependent offers, if the system operator notifies the aggregator for an offer activation. This process is repeated every day.

The minimum bid (2) required to cover the industry's costs when activating the flexibility offer may vary depending on the *MC*, making it difficult for the market to accept the offer if it is too high. A study has been conducted to mitigate the problem of high bids. It has been sought to maximize the offered capacity over all possible T_A without modifying day-ahead production, thereby ensuring a *MC* of zero. To do this, a constraint has been added to the flexibility model that fixes the flexibility load after the day-ahead, to be the same as the baseline load.

3. Results

Demand data from SPS has been provided for several weeks of 2023 over the optimization time horizon. For each of these weeks, the same scheduling has been optimized with different price curves, and flexibility offers have been generated for the day-ahead market in the mFRR service currently available in Spain.

Fig. 2 (a) Baseline (solid) and flexibility (dashed) load curves of the day-ahead production with LRC during *FP* and a T_A at 14h. (b) Baseline and flexibility day-ahead scheduling with production states (grey), set-ups states (light grey) and stop states (white)

Fig. 2 shows a representation of the LRC across the 4 lines for the day-ahead of one of the optimizations, and the impact on the planning in the sequencing and initiation of production batches. As observed, the load curve follows the baseline planning until the T_A of the flexibility offer, with a consumption reduction during the *FP* of 321 kW. Here, the batches from line 1 and 2 have been stopped mid-production. In Fig. 2 production is not recovered during the day-ahead, but within the 5-day horizon time.

3.1. Flexibility offers with affected day-ahead production

Various independent flexibility offers that can be made throughout 2023 are depicted in Fig. 3. As it can be seen, the bid offers on the x-axis, calculated with (2), depend on the additional *MC* that the industry incurs, such as stock costs, in order to modify day-ahead production to generate a flexibility offer. Offering a maximum LRC often incurs costs that are compensated by a high bid. Moreover, the high bids are penalized with no probability of being accepted. The acceptance probability is calculated based on the marginal bid price from generators' offers, from the mFRR service auction in the Spanish market, available at [9]. In this framework, a single offer sent to the aggregator would be weighted, based on the aggregated offers of each small and medium-sized industry to be auctioned to the external market.

Fig. 3 (a) Profit (dashed with triangle markers) and *MCs* (solid with circle markers) from each bid. (b) Probability of the offer being accepted (dashed with triangle markers) and LRC (solid with circle markers) from each bid

The offers with high bids occur when interrupting production to obtain LRCs, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The offer with the highest activation probability (97.95%) is for a LRC of 337 kWh, with a bid of 13.95 €/MWh and a profit of 4.7 €. Unlike the others, this offer is executed without interrupting production, but rather by delaying the production batch within hours of the day-ahead, ensuring the expected production for that day to be met. This delay mechanism motivates a proposed strategy for seeking bids at lower costs for the industry, with a higher likelihood of acceptance by the BSMs.

3.2. Flexibility offers without affected day-ahead production

Fig. 4 shows the new results of the flexibility offers for the same days as the offers generated in Fig. 3. The possible offers to make are fewer due to the machines being almost at full capacity during the day-ahead or the production batch being

started at a time making it impossible to stop without modifying the day-ahead production.

The activation probabilities have increased, but the profit obtained is lower due to the little capacity offered, compared with the results in Fig. 3. With no mid-production stops, the only way to generate LRCs is by delaying production batches within the day-ahead, thus most of the capacity offer comes from expected baseline set-up batches. By doing so, it can be seen that the MC is zero in all offers. The bid only needs to compensate for the cost increase with the, as represented by the numerator of equation (2). The load reduction offers shown in Fig. 4 originate from production batches with similar set-up consumptions. This strategy allows for few profits but ensures that small and medium-size industries can participate and generate revenue from ancillary services.

Fig. 4 (a) Profit (dashed with triangle markers) and MC s (solid with circle markers) from each bid, without modifying the day-ahead production. (b) Probability of the offer being accepted (dashed with triangle markers) and LRC (solid with circle markers) from each bid, without modifying the day-ahead production

4. Conclusion

While offering demand-side flexibility can present a revenue opportunity for small or medium-sized energy-oriented industries, it may be limited in scenarios where industries operate continuous processes or are near full capacity. For these industries, limitations arise from the relatively small profit margin compared to the technical complexity involved in providing such services and obtaining accurate spot market predictions. The case study analysed uses a RTP tariff, but other tariffs such as TOU could benefit more from this strategy where electricity prices are fixed during specific hours of the day. This could allow for multiple optimal baseline solutions that could serve as different flexibility offers at zero cost.

Results show how MC s associated with production changes for providing such flexibility are key. These costs incentivize the generation of offers that avoid advancing or delaying

production batches beyond the day-ahead, thus maintaining planned production of the baseline whenever possible. Although the benefits obtained from the last proposed strategy are low, they do not pose a significant management complication for small or middle-sized industries, since the planned production throughout the day-ahead is not modified and the LRCs are made where the planning has the capacity to do so without modifying the schedule or availability of workers. This last strategy could open the door to new hubs of small and medium-sized non-energy intensive industries that can compete in BSMs with the help of aggregators, to enhance hosting grid capacity.

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